

Conceptualisations of leadership that are most effective in school self-evaluation in post-primary schools in the Republic of Ireland

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Abstract

School Self-Evaluation (SSE) is an evidence-based approach to quality improvement of educational provision that can lead to enhanced learner experience and outcomes and improved school performance. Compulsory SSE has entered its third cycle in post-primary schools in Ireland: the first cycle occurred from 2012-2016; the second from 2016-2020 was extended because of the Covid-19 pandemic; and the third cycle runs from September 2022-June 2026. While distributed leadership is posited as the response to how school leaders can most effectively lead the SSE process, little is known about what precise conceptualisations of leadership are most effective in SSE. This paper hopes to explore how impactful distributed leadership is on the SSE process. Being a first year EdD student allows me to draw on my own professional practice as a principal in a small post-primary school in Ireland. A discussion of the key findings of the literature will first be presented. In particular this paper will present an analysis of teacher leadership and managerial leadership. I conclude by suggesting that these types of leadership work best with regards to SSE when operated through a lens of distributed leadership.

Key Words

School self-evaluation, distributed leadership, teacher leadership, managerial leadership

Three key highlights

- This paper highlights the challenge of unclear definitions of educational leadership in national and international educational discourse.
- This paper argues that managerial leadership and teacher leadership cultivated through a lens of distributed leadership can best serve the SSE process in post-primary schools in the Republic of Ireland.
- This paper concludes that conceptual models of leadership can only be successful in practice if there are shared values leading to a common vision for the school.

Introduction

The significance of educational leadership in schools has grown considerably in terms of its policy development, conceptualisation, operation and theoretical and empirical research in recent years (Bush and Glover, 2014). An obstacle to educational discourse involving leadership, however, surrounds the lack of clarity around the fundamental concept of educational leadership both nationally and internationally (Torrance and Humes, 2015). The varying and multitudinous nature of the labels used to define educational leadership contributes to this lack of clarity. The labels used to define this field have moved from ‘administration’ to ‘management’ to ‘leadership’ over the past eighty years (Gunter, 2004). While acknowledging the fact that there are over 350 definitions of leadership in the field of education and, indeed, the subjective nature of these definitions, Bush & Glover (2014) share the following ‘working definition’:

Leadership is a process of influence leading to the achievement of desired purposes. Successful leaders develop a vision for their schools based on their personal and professional values. They articulate this vision at every opportunity and influence their staff and other stakeholders to share the vision. The philosophy, structures and activities of the school are geared towards the achievement of this shared vision (Bush and Glover, 2014, p. 3).

While this three-dimensional conceptualisation of leadership provides a necessary and useful lens through which educational leadership can be examined in a broad sense, this analysis will

focus on contemporary discourses of educational leadership in the post-primary sector in the Republic of Ireland. Bush and Glover's (2014) emphasis on purpose, values, vision and influence will inform this analysis which is written from the perspective of a practicing post-primary principal. Specifically, it will explore the discourse surrounding school leadership and the school self-evaluation (SSE) process. Bush and Glover (2014) suggest the existence of nine leadership theories: Instructional leadership, managerial leadership, transformational leadership, moral or values leadership, distributed leadership, teacher leadership, system leadership, contingent leadership and authentic leadership. Drawing on my professional experience as a leader, some of those models are particularly useful when effectively leading the school self-evaluation process, namely, managerial leadership and teacher leadership. With regards to SSE these types of leadership work best when operated through a lens of distributed leadership (Morrissey, 2021).

Managerial leadership

International comparisons of educational attainment have increased the importance placed on school improvement to allow countries to perform competitively on a global stage (Torrance and Humes, 2015; Skerritt *et al.*, 2021). While SSE was a feature in Irish schools since 2003 when the first quality framework was published, the process became a formal requirement of schools in 2012 when SSE was re-introduced as a collaborative, inclusive, internal process of review and reflection leading to considered action and school improvement. This evidence-based approach to quality improvement of educational provision can lead to enhanced learner experience and outcomes and improved school performance (O'Brien *et al.*, 2022). While much progress has been made in the last ten years, an initial lack of clarity around roles and responsibilities, a moratorium on middle leadership appointments and a global pandemic have provided challenges to embedding the process fully in schools (Barry *et al.*, 2022).

Given the low-stakes accountability of the internal SSE process and the external inspection process in Ireland, the approach to SSE by schools has been inconsistent. It is noteworthy also, that research has found that SSE is not necessarily popular with the majority of staff in Irish schools and that school leaders are often more enthusiastic than teachers towards the process (Harvey, 2015; Skerritt *et al.*, 2021). Yet since engagement in the SSE process is now compulsory, school leaders must ensure compliance throughout their schools (Skerritt *et al.*, 2021). Managerial leadership in education is associated with the roles, duties and behaviours that leaders must carry out in order to support the work of others to achieve the smooth running of the organisation (Bush and Glover, 2014). This model of leadership closely aligns with the formal legislative roles and responsibilities of school principals as outlined for the first time in the Education Act, Sections (22) and (23) (Government of Ireland, 1998). Managerial leadership lends itself to this focus on efficiency but in doing so, there is a fear that its adherence to rigid planning and target-setting regimes conflicts with the traditional value system of schools (Simkins, 2005). This model of leadership must co-exist with strong values if it is to be successful in an education setting (Bush and Glover, 2014). This is particularly true in post-primary schools in Ireland where graduates enter the teaching profession with laudable altruistic intentions (Heinz, 2013). Such employees respond better to a model of leadership that is rooted in authentic, inclusive, community values of care and equality, for example distributed leadership.

Distributed leadership

The Department of Education's (DE) Circular 003/2018 entitled "Leadership and Management in Post-Primary Schools" outlined a model and process that redefined the leadership and management functions of post holders in post-primary schools when it obliged schools to employ a model of distributed school leadership (Department of Education & Skills, 2018).

The Department of Education (DE) Inspectorate published *Looking at our School (2016) A Quality Framework for Post- Primary Schools (LAOS)* which was updated in 2022 and supplied a set of standards for two key areas of the work of schools: teaching and learning, and leadership and management. The leadership and management dimension details four domains to evaluate leadership practice in post-primary schools: Leading learning and teaching, managing the organisation, leading school development and developing leadership capacity (Department of Education, 2022). This provides the framework against which the SSE process for school improvement is employed through the distributed leadership model (Murphy, 2020). It notes that ‘school leaders’ typically refers to formal leadership roles including “school patrons/trustees, boards of management, principals and deputy principals. It also includes teachers with posts of responsibility and those who have undertaken roles related to the school’s priorities” (Department of Education, 2022, p. 10). It also explicitly outlines the leadership role for all teachers within the school. The literature argues, however, that such a leadership role does not ‘reflect the realities of [all] teachers’ professional aspirations, identities and practices’ (Torrance, 2013, p. 354).

Similar to educational leadership and managerial leadership, there is a tension surrounding the lack of a shared understanding about the conceptualisation and operation of distributed leadership, even amongst school principals (Harris and DeFlaminis, 2016; Murphy and Brennan, 2022). Circular 003/2018 did not provide the required clarity in terms of the enactment of distributed leadership (Department of Education & Skills, 2018). Distributed leadership practice involves the important interaction between school leaders, their followers and their situation (Spillane, 2005). Leithwood, Harris and Hopkins (2019) confirmed that school leadership “has a greater influence on schools and students where it is widely distributed” (p. 12). They noted that much of the criticism of distributed leadership, which ironically condemned its lack of empirical evidence, was also not soundly based on evidence

itself (Leithwood, Harris and Hopkins, 2019). Hulpia and Davos (2010) identified the importance of the quality and distribution of the leadership functions, along with relationships and co-operation in distributed leadership. Likewise, Deflaminis (2013) found that distributed leadership worked best when the hierarchical structure of leadership was flattened and people were allowed to lead because of their expertise rather than their position. Lumby (2013) also cautions the ways power is enacted in the theorisation of distributed leadership. At its best, distributed leadership considers where people's strengths lie and provides opportunities for them to lead in their areas of interest and expertise. This is particularly useful when teachers are empowered to work in teams to co-create, evaluate and update school wide improvement plans as part of the SSE process.

Empowering teacher leadership

Distributed leadership will only be successfully assimilated into schools if there are teacher leaders who take ownership of this organisational framework (Bush and Glover, 2014). The SSE process, though often led by a formal post-holder, relies on teams of teachers to take charge of embedding developments in teaching, learning and assessment in a school-wide manner. Professional learning and sustainable change happen when teachers reflect on their current practice in the light of the needs of their students in order to identify ways to improve (Torrance and Humes, 2015). Teacher leadership requires teachers to develop curricular and pedagogical excellence within their own classroom and beyond to influence the practice of others. It happens when teachers move beyond the classroom to share best practice and introduce new developments (Harris and Jones, 2019). Teacher leadership can involve student teachers on school placements, newly qualified teachers, and teachers who do not wish to continue to formal leadership positions (Murphy, 2020).

Like educational leadership, managerial leadership and distributed leadership, the conceptualisation of teacher leadership poses challenges. Crowther, Ferguson and Hann argue:

Teacher leadership is a particular form of school leadership different from, yet highly dependent on metastrategic principal leadership. For it to exist at all, moderate encouragement and support from administrators is required. For it to thrive, substantial encouragement and support are often necessary (Crowther, Ferguson and Hann, 2009, p. 140).

Leithwood and Mascall (2008) claim that leadership hierarchies are necessary in schools for sustainable coordination and strategic direction to take place. The hierarchical positioning of leadership within the educational paradigm identifies leaders and followers but does not allow for the complexity and nuances of the labour process (Torrance and Humes, 2015). Indeed, there is often a symbiotic relationship between leader and follower where leaders are equally influenced by followers (Spillane, 2005). This is particularly true in the SSE process where the participation of teachers, parents and students are necessary to determine the meaningful developments that could take place to improve the collective learner experience. Teacher leadership is especially important in the SSE process because it has the potential to affect whole-school learning, teaching and assessment through developing teacher agency and teacher cooperation (Harris and Muijs, 2004). It is also seen as a model of leadership which empowers teachers, improves self-esteem and employee fulfilment and increases motivation and performance (Katzenmeyer and Moller, 2009).

A distributed model of leadership in schools assumes the empowerment of teachers (Barry *et al.*, 2022). Core characteristics of empowering leadership include “encouraging self-leadership and participation, conveying confidence, granting autonomy, and enhancing job meaningfulness” (Kim and Beehr, 2021, p. 31). While distributed leadership can be viewed as the structural consideration of the functions and obligations of a learning organisation, empowering leadership involves the “micropolitics of purposeful interactions among

individuals within a learning organisation” (Barry *et al.*, 2022, p.2). There is an expectation that the school leader is adept at building relationships. This can be emotionally demanding and have detrimental effects if the principal does not have an understanding of and seek to nourish these relationship building skills (Maxwell and Riley, 2017). SSE is an innovative opportunity for teacher leaders to affect change in their schools. The literature, however, suggests that much work needs to be done to understand the practice of school leadership if this is to become a reality (Torrance, 2013).

Conclusion

Managerial leadership and teacher leadership cultivated through a lens of distributed leadership can best serve school improvement policies enacted through the SSE process in the post-primary sector in the Republic of Ireland. Circular 0003/2018 points to distributed leadership as the lens through which this leadership should be enacted in schools. Leadership must be embedded both horizontally (teacher) and vertically (managerial) in school organisations within a distributed leadership perspective if the SSE process is to be successful as a tool for school improvement. These conceptual models can only come to life if the leadership is authentic and able to build a relational trust with the partners in education, including all school staff, to co-create shared values leading to a common vision for the school. Managerial leadership and teacher leadership which is nurtured through a culture of distributed leadership has influenced this researcher's work as a professional leader in the SSE process. Future research could explore the role of authentic leadership in building trust and shared values in educational settings. Such leadership would inspire motivation, participation, and collaboration to achieve collective goals and school improvement.

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